

Stability of the ternary copper(II) complexes involving tertiary diimines and a vitamin B₆ derivative

Neelima D. Kulkarni

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, M. S. University of Baroda, Vadodara-390 002, India

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The stability constants of the ternary complexes of copper(II) with pyridoxal (vitamin B₆ analogue) and tertiary diimines (A), 2,2'-bipyridyl, 1,10-phenanthroline, 5-nitro-1,10-phenanthroline and bis(2-pyridyl)amine, have been determined by potentiometry and their redox behaviour at mercury electrode has been examined. The potentiometric titrations have been carried out at 30° in 50% (v/v) aqueous dioxane at 0.2 M NaClO₄. The log K_{MAL}^M values determined by considering the existence of all possible species in solution follow a definite order. The cyclic voltammograms recorded at the optimum pH in the aqueous solutions indicate quasireversible redox processes at the HMD electrode.

The extensive studies being carried out since last several years with the transition metal ions and biologically important ligands in solution are mainly aimed at unfolding the role of the metal-ligand equilibria in the proceedings of the biochemical reactions¹. Understanding the effects of intramolecular interligand interactions and non-interacting substituents in the ligands on the stability of the ternary complexes becomes necessary before extending any model to a real metalloprotein. This is because such studies can explain the role of substituents and prosthetic groups in deciding the reactivity and selectivity of the metalloenzymes towards certain substrates. Amine oxidases are believed to involve copper(II) and pyridoxal as cofactors². With protein environment having various N-containing chelating sites, the study of equilibrium involving such sites, pyridoxal and copper(II) becomes important.

Present study is an attempt to evaluate the effect of the presence of tertiary diimines on the equilibria involving copper-pyridoxal by way of determining the stability constants of the ternary complexes, [Cu(*tert*-diimine) (pyridoxal)] (Fig. 1), and their redox properties at mercury electrode.

Results and Discussion

The stability constants of the ternary complexes were determined using two approaches : (1) formation of [CuAL]⁺ in two steps, (a) Cu + A → [CuA] and (b) CuA + L ⇌ [CuAL], and (2) simultaneous reaction between the metal ion and two ligands resulting in the existence of various species, namely, AH⁺, A, LH₂⁺, LH, L⁻, Cu²⁺, [CuA]²⁺, [CuL]⁺, [CuA₂]²⁺, [CuL₂] and [CuAL]⁺. (Herein-after the charges on the species are omitted for convenience). The log K_{MAL}^M values obtained by the two methods agree well indicating that the formation of [CuA] is almost complete at the pH where it starts combining with pyridoxal. The stepwise reaction is also supported by the species distribution as a function of pH (Fig. 2). The formation constants and the uniformly positive Δ log K values

Fig. 1.

Table 1. Dissociation constants of pyridoxal and the formation constants of the binary complexes with copper(II) at 30°

	Medium*	Constants
pK_1^H	(A)	8.55 ± 0.07
	(B)	8.54 ± 0.02
$-\log \beta_2^H$	(A)	13.05 ± 0.09
	(B)	13.04 ± 0.03
$\log K_{Cu}^{Cu}$	(A)	4.39 ± 0.90
	(B)	4.65 ± 0.24
$\log K_{Cu}^{Cu(pyxl)_2}$	(A)	8.47 ± 0.54
	(B)	8.68 ± 0.30

* (A) = 25% Dioxane-water; (B) 50% dioxane-water.

Fig. 2. Species distribution in Cu-dpa-pyxl : (-) free Cu^{II}, (.....) [CuA], (.....) [CuA₂], (.....) [Cu pyxl], (-.-) [Cu(pyxl)₂], (---) [CuA pyxl].

indicate that the ternary [CuA pyridoxal] complexes are more stable than the corresponding binary complexes. This is due to the high π -bonding ability of the tertiary diimines.

The coordination of tertiary diimine with copper(II) results in an increase in Class A character (σ -bonding ability) of copper(II) due to metal $d\pi \rightarrow$ ligand π^* -electron flow. Thus, the metal ion, now, has an increased tendency to coordinate with a hard base (i.e. a σ -donor) like pyridoxal which coordinates with the metal ion through the carbonyl O and the phenolate O⁻. In other words, when pyridoxal coordinates with copper(II) the ligand electrons have to face repulsion with the $d\pi$ electrons of the metal ion. However, in presence of a tertiary diimine the $d\pi$ electron density of the metal ion gets delocalised over the diimine ligand and hence, the incoming pyridoxal ligand has to face less repulsion. This results in the enhanced stability of the ternary complex. Pyridoxal too has some π -bonding ability and hence the synergic stabilisation of M-A and M-pyridoxal bonds in the ternary complexes is finely 'tuned' according to the nature of A.

The order of stabilisation, i.e. $\Delta \log K$, is found to be [Cu dpa pyxl] \approx [Cu bipy pyxl] < [Cu N-phen pyxl] > [Cu phen pyxl]. Bis(2-pyridyl)amine has NH group with inductive electron-releasing and mesomeric electron-withdrawing character and hence it has equivalent stabilising effect

Table 2. Stability constants of the ternary complexes [CuA (pyxl)] in aqueous dioxane (1 : 1, v/v) medium at 30°

Compd.	Species considered	$\log K_{CuA}^{CuA pyxl}$	$\log K_{CuA}^{CuA pyxl}$	$\Delta \log K$
[Cu dpa pyxl]	(1) H ₂ L, HL, L, CuA, CuAL	5.19 ± 0.41	-	+0.54
	(2) HA, A, H ₂ L, HL, L, Cu, CuA, CuA ₂ , CuL, CuL ₂ , CuAL	-	12.56 ± 0.22	+0.62
[Cu bipy pyxl]	(1) H ₂ L, HL, L, CuA, CuAL	5.25 ± 0.20	-	+0.60
	(2) HA, A, H ₂ L, HL, L, Cu, CuA, CuA ₂ , CuL, CuL ₂ , CuAL	-	12.28 ± 0.18	+0.63
[Cu phen pyxl]	(1) H ₂ L, HL, L, CuA, CuAL	4.95 ± 0.26	-	+0.30
	(2) HA, A, H ₂ L, HL, L, Cu, CuA, CuA ₂ , CuL, CuL ₂ , CuAL	-	13.79 ± 0.02	+0.32
[Cu N-phen pyxl]	(1) H ₂ L, HL, L, CuA, CuAL	5.42 ± 0.16	-	+0.77
	(2) HA, A, H ₂ L, HL, L, Cu, CuA, CuA ₂ , CuL, CuL ₂ , CuAL	-	12.03 ± 12	+0.82

Table 3. Redox potentials of the binary and the ternary complexes of pyridoxal

	pH	(A)		(B)		(C)	
		E_{pc}	E_{pa}	E_{pc}	E_{pa}	E_{pc}	E_{pa}
Cu ²⁺	4.0	-0.01	+0.07	-	-	-	-
	5.0	-0.005	+0.04	-	-	-	-
	6.0	-0.01	+0.04	-	-	-	-
[Cu pyxl]	4.0	+0.01	+0.08	-	-	-	-
	5.0	+0.01	+0.05	-	-	-	-
	6.0	+0.01	+0.04	-	-	-	-
[Cu bipy]	4.0	+0.03	-0.08	-0.09	-0.02	-	-
	6.0	+0.005	+0.04	-0.115	-0.05	-	-
[Cu dpa]	4.0	-0.05	+0.03*	-	-	-	-
	5.0	-	-	-0.085	-0.025	-	-
[Cu bipy pyxl]	4.0	+0.02	+0.08	-0.09	-0.02	-	-
	6.0	0.0	+0.04	-0.125	-0.05	-0.32	-0.25
[Cu dpa pyxl]	5.0	+0.01	+0.05	-0.07	-0.02	-0.12	-
	6.0	0.0	+0.05	-0.07	-0.03	-0.20	-0.16

(1) E_p values recorded at the scan rates 20–200 mV s⁻¹ vary only within ± 10 mV unless otherwise stated; values above are at 100 mV s⁻¹. *This splits into 2 peaks in subsequent scans

like 2,2'-bipyridyl 5-Nitro-1,10-phenanthroline with electron-withdrawing NO_2 group and maximum π -bonding ability forms the most stable complex.

Voltammetric studies : The cyclic voltammetric studies are restricted to the binary and ternary complexes containing bipy and dpa since the reduction of the complexes containing phen and N-phen are highly dominated by adsorption on the working electrode.

The cyclic voltammograms of the solutions containing only copper(II) ion and copper(II) and pyridoxal at pHs 4, 5 and 6 are identical under the conditions of the experiment and consist of only one almost reversible process (1) ($I_{pc}/I_{pa} \approx 1$) at scan rates 20 to 200 mV s^{-1} . This is expected because the formation of $[\text{Cu pyxl}]$ is negligible upto pH 6 as indicated by the species distribution curves. It can also be seen from the species distribution curves that in the solutions containing copper(II) perchlorate, pyridoxal and ligand A, $[\text{CuA}]$ is the dominating species with >80% concentration at pH 4.0 which gradually decreases to ~60% at pH 6.0. The concentration of $[\text{CuAL}]$ increases from ~5% at pH 5.0 to 25–35% at pH 6.0. The concentrations of Cu^{2+} and $[\text{CuA}_2]$ are less than 5% and $[\text{CuL}]$, $[\text{CuL}_2]$ are <1%. Thus the voltammograms of these solutions can be conveniently used for determining the redox potentials corresponding to the $[\text{CuAL}]$ species

The voltammograms of the solutions containing copper(II) perchlorate and bipy consist of a reversible process (B) corresponding to $[\text{Cu bipy}]^{2+/1+}$ and another small peak corresponding to free Cu^{2+} (A). In the solutions containing copper(II) perchlorate and dpa only the redox processes corresponding to $[\text{Cu dpa}]^{2+/1+}$ is observed at pHs 4.0 and 5.0, the amount of free Cu^{2+} being negligible in the solution.

In the solutions containing copper(II) perchlorate, pyxl and bipy/dpa, two cathodic peaks and the corresponding anodic processes are observed at pH 4.0–6.0. In addition, a third couple (C) with high I_{pc}/I_{pa} starts appearing at pH 5.0 and becomes predominant at pH 6.0. This can be assigned to $[\text{Cu A pyxl}]^{1+/0}$ process. The E_p values corresponding to $[\text{Cu bipy pyxl}]$ are more negative compared to the values for $[\text{Cu dpa pyxl}]$. This is indicative of a stronger π -interaction in the dpa complex although both the ligand \rightarrow metal σ - and metal \rightarrow ligand π -interactions are finely tuned with each other to result in equivalent amount of stabilisation, $\Delta \log K$, in the two complexes.

Experimental

Bis(2-pyridyl)amine (A^1) (Fluka), 2,2'-bipyridyl (A^2) (B D.H.), 1,10-phenanthroline (A^3) (Merck), 5-nitro-1,10-

phenanthroline (A^4) (Sigma) and pyridoxal hydrochloride (H_2L) (Merck) were of A R grade and used as such

Potentiometric studies : The formation constants of the ternary complexes $[\text{CuAL}]$ were determined at 30° by titrating potentiometrically, 50% (v/v) aqueous dioxane solutions containing copper perchlorate, the two ligands (all 0.001 M) and perchloric acid (0.02 M) with 0.2 M NaOH using glass electrode and a pH meter (accuracy ± 0.01). The ionic strength of the solutions was maintained at 0.2 M (NaClO_4) and the observed pH values were corrected to eliminate the liquid-junction potentials by comparing the pH of the perchloric acid solutions having different concentrations in 50% aqueous dioxane with the calculated values of the hydrogen ion activity³. The titration data were processed to get the stability constant values using the program SCOGS⁴. The dissociation constants of pyridoxal and the formation constants of the binary complexes with copper(II) were determined in 25 and 50% aqueous dioxane media under the same conditions. These are recorded in Table 1. The values of $\log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{M}}$ and $\Delta \log K$ ($= \log K_{\text{MAL}}^{\text{M}} - \log K_{\text{MA}}^{\text{M}} - \log K_{\text{ML}}^{\text{M}}$) are recorded in Table 2.

Voltammetric studies . The cyclic voltammograms of the solutions containing copper perchlorate and the two ligands (0.001 M each) in water at pHs 4.0, 5.0 and 6.0 (0.1 M acetate buffer) were recorded using a PAR 174A polarographic analyser equipped with PAR 175 programmer and 303A electrode assembly. The experiments were carried out under dinitrogen atmosphere with HMD working electrode, Pt-wire as counter electrode and Ag/AgCl as reference electrode. The results are summarised in Table 3.

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